

Collective Creativity in the Lecture Hall: Key Issues, Participant Strategies and Aesthetic Challenges

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Abstract

Collective creativity (CC) in the context of a theatre production course at the Université d'Abomey-Calavi (Republic of Benin) brings together categories of people from diverse backgrounds who are motivated by different issues. This includes teachers, students and representatives of the academic institution (head of department, faculty dean, etc.). Given the range of profiles involved in the artistic journey, it is worth asking how the diverse expectations of people participating in this experience can be reconciled to ensure that a production has the necessary dramatic qualities. Far from being obstacles to the practical teaching of theatre, the sometimes conflicting interactions are the CC's driving force, one that the lecturer must manage with tact and efficacy. The corroboration of this hypothesis is the springboard to achieving two objectives: first, to identify participant strategies and challenges; and second, to analyse the methodology used in the university's creative theatre workshops. Lastly, this study, which applies Bourdieu's theory of the literary field, confirms the types of strategy used by participants in the theatre project as well as the aesthetic challenges faced and the methodology employed to overcome them.

Introduction

If theatre continues to be taught in the same way as traditional arts and humanities disciplines – in other words, like a literary text – then everything is just fine. But if a lecturer broaches the performance component by making students watch a show, or better still by making them take to the stage, that lecturer will face questions from their academic institution, their

students and even from him/herself. These questions are particularly abundant when this experience comprises collective creativity (CC). This type of creative production enables the analysis of a whole range of issues that transform the stage into a space of diverse interests, given the risk of dismissing certain aesthetic concerns in favour of a performance focused more on personal, ideological and/or political issues. Of course, this diversity of issues is consubstantial with every creative theatrical project, but it is amplified and further complicated in a pedagogical context – in the university education system, to be precise. How can the diverse expectations of people involved in this experience be reconciled to ensure that the production has the necessary dramatic qualities? It could be said that these sometimes conflicting interactions, far from being obstacles to the practical teaching of theatre, may actually be the CC's driving force, one that the lecturer needs to manage with tact and efficacy.

The two objectives of this study are to identify participant strategies and challenges, and then to analyse the methodology used in the university's creative theatre workshops.¹

Furthermore, focusing on a subject such as this could attract critics interested in research into collective creations developed in a learning environment where pupils or students are deeply involved in all aspects of production. In terms of research, a literature review and unstructured interviews were first carried out before literary theory was applied to the analysis of two CC case studies produced as part of a module delivered in the Département des Lettres Modernes (DLM; Modern Languages Department) entitled "Mise en scène: de la scène au texte" (Theatre Production: From Stage to Page). The department is part of the Faculté des Lettres, Langues, Arts et Communication (FLLAC; Faculty of Literature, Languages, Arts and Communication) at the former Université Nationale du Bénin (National University of Benin), now the Université d'Abomey-Calavi (UAC). Participant observation was also used as I was involved in the creative process in my capacity as a lecturer.² This article begins with an introduction to the main corpus, which is then followed by an analysis of the creative processes and strategies employed to develop the two plays. Finally, there is an exploration of aesthetic challenges and the way they were managed.

Summary of the Theatre Production Module and Corpus

The theatre production module was introduced to the DLM at UAC in the 2015–16 academic year and led to the production of two plays.

The Theatre Production Module: A Pedagogical Innovation

Despite the existence of the Faculté des Lettres, Arts et Sciences Humaines (FLASH; Faculty of Literature, Arts and Humanities) at the former National University of Benin, created in 1970, there was a 40-year wait before the university opened an arts department in 2010. The latter was converted into the Institut National des Métiers d'Arts, d'Archéologie et de la Culture (INMAAC; National Institute of Professional Arts, Archaeology and Culture) in 2015. The lack of the human, material and financial resources required to create such an institute and make it functional partly explains this delay.³ However, for five decades, French-language theatre has been taught in the DLM. But the emphasis has mostly been placed on the study of theatrical literature; the staging aspect has been overlooked due to the lack of lecturers to teach it. In 2015, thanks to reforms in the higher education system, FLASH split into two autonomous entities: FLLAC and the Faculté des Sciences Humaines et Sociales (Faculty of Human and Social Sciences). From the start of the 2015–16 academic year and in line with the bachelor's–master's–doctorate education system (BMD, known as *le système LMD* in French), a new learning provision was formulated for the six-semester bachelor's degree. A module entitled “Theatre Production” was created for semesters 3–4 and 5–6. It comprises four 25-hour modules, including “Theatre Production: From Stage to Page” delivered in semester 6. The aim of the module is to guide learners towards identifying steps to be taken when staging a theatre production employing CC, defined as “all group productions in which actors, especially by means of improvisation, are more than simple interpreters, and where all participants have contributed to the creation of the performance”⁴ (Hébert 1977, 45). The meticulous organisation of work is therefore required for this creative process.

Practical Organisation of Work and Facilitation of Sessions

In terms of process, CC introduces a series of integrated complex mechanisms to help individuals gather resources and unite around the development of a theatrical project, collectively exploring all dramatic components (discursive, scenographic, gestural, technical, etc.) in a gradual and continuous way and with a theatrical performance and/or text as the key objective.⁵ Pierre Rousseau identifies eight stages in this process: research and choice of theme, thematic research (gathering information on the theme), discussion and sharing of ideas, thematic framework (outline of the play being created), call for feedback (addressed to external people to help decide on the show under construction), regrouping of the creative

team, external assistance (another call for feedback on the show), acting, and then critique (the first four performances are put on for the purpose of gathering public opinion) (Rousseau 1979).

When it came to our project, we used a different approach but with the same aims – namely, creative freedom, improvisation and inclusive participation. With this in mind, and contrary to Rousseau, we dismissed the whole idea of a “thematic framework” before the creative process. There was no pre-established plan; the show took shape through improvisation and trial and error on stage.

At the start of the course, the lecturer-coordinator introduced the syllabus, then the students were free to work through proposals and vote on the choice of subject while under the supervision of the lecturer. Always with his support, they identified and created work groups: directors/producers, musicians/choreographers, actors, sound and light directors, scenographers and costume designers, and transcribers/writers. The latter took notes and extricated the play’s text from the performance after it was put together. The groups were formed only as a guide, because, during rehearsals and in light of the potential shown by any individual, the groups could register the arrival of new members or the departure of former participants.

The programme for each session, established by the lecturer-coordinator, was the same: after a “warm-up” run by the musicians/choreographers, the actors started to perform and members of the other groups followed, making observations and offering feedback and suggestions. These initial steps led to the production of two plays: *Roi LMD International* (*King BMD International*, henceforth *RLI*) and *Les Chaussures de Maman* (*Mum’s Shoes*, henceforth *LCM*). Created in December 2017, *RLI* has already been performed at least six times in different towns and cities across Benin (Calavi, Cotonou, Porto-Novo, Houégbo). *LCM* has been performed only once, on the Abomey-Calavi university campus in July 2019.

Roi LMD International and Les Chaussures de Maman: Two Socio-Political Satires

RLI is a one-hour show and opens with four students arriving in the lecture hall: Student 1 (Patrice Ogou), Student 2 (Jérôme Gbêwa), Student 3 (Prisca Godonou) and Student 4 (Césaire Houindo). They criticise the inflated number of students and the shortfall of teaching personnel. Then they appear in the library, where they come face to face over the only available book. Suddenly, the police appear due to the noise they are making. During the

night, the students spread human excrement everywhere in retaliation and organise a strange scatological competition. However, their amusement soon wanes when Student 1 steals the other three students' parcels of excrement. Although he has been exposed, he still commands respect from his peers due to his occult threats and his role as a spy for the president's political party. Giving in to his coercion, the others crown him *Roi LMD International* and beg him to return their parcels. But he won't have time to do it; the invalidation of the academic year is announced on the radio. Dejected, the other students fall to their knees and ask the university authorities for their forgiveness for the violence they have caused.

LCM is more politically engaged and the show lasts approximately 45 minutes. For some time, the mother of a happy family has been serving as president of the Republic when she shows up somewhere wearing high-heeled shoes. She has six children: Child 1 (Grâce Dossou), Child 2 (Marius Affantondji), Child 3 (Nadège Zannou), Child 4 (Estamine Mito-Baba), Child 5 (Paul Tchando) and Child 6 (Gilbert Akotognon). They approach their mother one by one, congratulating her on the shoes she is parading proudly. And lacking any historical awareness, they also commend her positive track record as the country's leader. Only one of them reveals that she is guilty of corruption, high treason and perjury. Amid angry protests, the mother calls for the cautionary punishment of the renegade. But her duplicity is suddenly exposed when she is trying to adjust her *pagne* and, unintentionally, loads of banknotes fall on the floor, revealing that the accusations made against her were true. Taking advantage of the shock of those around her, she slips away while her disillusioned children wail in despair.

The processes involved in creating the plays are related both to higher education and to the habitus of the individuals contributing.

Dynamic and Complex Creative Processes

We will, in part, draw our inspiration for the structure of this study from the steps recommended by Pascal Durand for applying theory in literary research (without adhering to his approach point by point). This requires making an inventory of higher education institutions, carrying out a comparative analysis of participants, creating a visual overview of their processes and habitus, defining their degree of autonomy, and then analysing the "system of aesthetic codes and rhetorical techniques" (Durand 2001, 37) – namely, the study of the aesthetic processes employed in creating the two plays.

The Field of Higher Education: An Overview

So, how is the field of state higher education in Benin best described? It is first worth noting that Benin is a country where the official language is French – the language of the former colonising power – but French coexists with around 50 local languages, the most widely spoken being Fon. And this field, which can be described as a “structure of objective relations helping to determine the concrete form of interactions” (Bourdieu 1998, 299) between academic institutions and their leaders, has two primary features: institutional proliferation and polymorphism. These can be seen in the very heart of the government ministry responsible for higher education and research, which supervises several administrative structures including the rectorate (Board of Education). At UAC, for example, the rector – who is supported by three vice-rectors – oversees the coordination of activities at school, institute and faculty levels. Each faculty is then administered by a dean, who oversees the management of departments, and each department is managed by a head and deputy head. In the DLM, the head and deputy head are responsible for the effective management of departmental administration and education, in particular for the smooth running of courses and student assessments. It may look as though learners are on the bottom rung of the ladder in the university environment, but that is not in fact the case. Like administrators and teaching personnel, they are organised into powerful unions such as the Union Nationale des Scolaires et Étudiants du Bénin (National Union for Schoolchildren and Students of Benin), and these unions are capable of taking action feared by all. Stemming from this, then, we can see a third distinctive feature: not a balance of power but rather a constant risk of conflict. Since 1990, violent demonstrations (led by such unions) putting forward various demands (holding retakes, ensuring regular grant payments, lowering registration fees, etc.) have marred the improving public image of the student, once considered to be that of a young dissenter during the dictatorship of the 1980s.⁶ The invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year (at the former faculty known as FLASH) only served to strengthen the mistrust of students, who from that point on were seen to be in allegiance with political parties and proponents of violence.⁷ The theatre workshops took place in light of this social context and the participants’ habitus – in other words, their “capital of informational models that enables them to produce sensible and regular thoughts and practices without any intention of behaving meaningfully and without consciously obeying rules explicitly posed as such” (Bourdieu 1990, 76).

Habitus and Strategic Positioning

The creative processes for both plays involved direct participants (students and the lecturer-coordinator) and indirect participants (teaching staff and those in charge of the faculty) as well as external collaborators (private cultural providers).

There were on average 120 students enrolled in semester 6 in each of the two year groups. They were aged between 20 and 30, speak French and at least one of Benin's national languages, and for the most part they had no theatre experience at all. Both men and women still remembered the invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year. Hence, they were frustrated young adults who saw the majority of teachers and those in the dean's office as obstacles to their success.⁸ This was evident from the accusatory and insulting graffiti on walls around the university and from the very hostile chanting directed at the aforementioned authorities and teachers during protests. In the group context of CC, their social capital was low: they had only their passion for the art, their availability, and their knowledge of student unions and endogenous oral literature. This was not the case for the lecturer-coordinator, who holds a doctorate in Theatre Studies, is a member of theatre organisations, and was the DLM's deputy head (May 2016–May 2019) and then head (since May 2019), as well as being an actor, director/producer and playwright.

However, indirect participants – i.e. other teaching staff – did not form a homogeneous unit. Depending on their habitus, their reactions towards the creative theatre workshops ranged from indifference to interested curiosity and even opposition. For example, the former DLM head (from May 2016 to May 2019) always came across as hostile to all forms of progressive collaboration with learners because a good number of students showed a lack of respect. Finally, our external collaborators were promoters of cultural spaces outside the university and, as few academic classrooms were free or suitable for theatrical creativity, these promoters were able to provide interpersonal and infrastructural capital. For example, *RLI* was developed in Abomey-Calavi at a private cultural centre called FESTHEC (Festival Scolaire et Universitaire de Théâtre et de Chorégraphie/School and University Festival of Theatre and Choreography). In addition, the promoters of these centres contributed a wealth of expertise by casting a critical eye on the creative processes as they took place. Their strategic positioning, like that of other participants, was constantly dependent on mutual relationships and underpinned by a range of different challenges.

Individual Challenges and Expectations

So, how did these different groups of people with such diverse profiles collaborate to develop and stage the two shows? The entire ensemble of students and the lecturer can be seen as one “latent group”, described as a “collection of individuals sharing a common characteristic” (Boudon and Bourricaud 1989, 18). The common characteristic, in this case, is the play being developed, and participants are constantly interacting with each another and with the other social categories (other lecturers and external collaborators), for they are involved not only in reciprocal actions, but also in “subjective meanings interpretable by different participants, that help them consider the behaviour of others and potentially modify their own” (Ferréol 2015, 145).

Using participant observation, we interpreted the actions of each individual and captured fragments of language used here and there. Thus, in accepting this collaboration, the primary objective for private cultural promoters was “the use of their space and the hope of building the foundations of a partnership with the Modern Languages Department or UAC”,⁹ a well-established institution. Resistant lecturers wanted to distance themselves from the withering image of the lecturer-researcher on stage, as well as the unsubstantiated celebrity standing of a horde of students who had been given “star” status¹⁰ among their peers. Their unresistant colleagues wanted to see this experience contribute “towards introducing the students to theatre practice by placing them at the heart of theatre processes” (Acakpo 2018, 2¹¹) and helping them:

discover the different stages in creating a piece of theatre, from choice of subject matter to the performance in front of an audience, including the casting of actors, formulating a storyline and writing the script, the set design, sound and lighting, choice of costumes, rehearsals, training actors, directing actors, producing the show, etc. (Acakpo 2018, 2)

This quote sums up the pedagogical aim of the module as established by the lecturer-coordinator, who was keen to achieve that objective at all costs. Finally, one important role of the creative workshops was to offer an element of “fun” to the students as “theatre is playful, so it has characteristics conducive to a fun activity: it is free and pleasurable” (Vigeant 1989, 121). The fun element is all the greater because CC is involved, and this leads us to the “debate on the supremacy of the literary text over the performance because it rightly

encourages a large part of the show to focus on the visual and fun components rather than on the intellectual component” (ibid., 122). We observed how the students took pleasure in mocking the late arrival of the lecturer and deriding the disrepair of the university library. In terms of fun, the play performed a psychological function as a “release”, thus bringing internal freedom: students were liberated from their frustrations through the art of theatre, taking symbolic revenge upon the academic institution that had seemingly ground them down. The creative workshops could be seen as a space where different strategies came together and were implemented by individuals equipped with a certain degree of power.

The Actors’ Strategies

A strategy is “any intervention oriented towards an objective and is dependent on matters to settle and issues to resolve” (Durand 2001, 25). A strategy is knowingly adopted by an actor; this idea, in its sociological sense, suggests “freedom of initiative, but also reserves of rational behaviour and, to be honest, [it] corresponds with the image of the modern individual” (Gaudin 2009, 7). In the margins of freedom, it can be seen that, despite the continual presence of the lecturer-coordinator, the students created their own strategies for the duration of the module and these can be put into five categories: acceptance, defection, opposition, avoidance or deception, and hijacking.

Acceptance, the most common form of cooperation, involves each participant agreeing to be part of the theatre project with the aim of making it successful by adopting the necessary attitudes. Student attendance was excellent during the academic year; they were always willing to look for extra slots in their timetable so they could advance their progress in the workshops. But despite this enthusiasm, the projects advanced rather laboriously, due to both students’ individual academic obligations (attending regular lessons, preparing for end-of-semester assessments, etc.) and their inexperience.

Towards the end of July in both 2017 and 2019, these pedagogical constraints were lifted. Final academic results had either been announced or were about to be. So, it was decided that students would continue their work on open-ended artistic projects after the end of the academic year. However, a fair number of learners left for the holidays (staying within the country), while others adopted a strategy of leaving the country. So, the number of attendees was cut by 15. For *RLI*, only a dozen young artists were consistent in their efforts and committed to attending rehearsals between July and December 2017; for *LCM*,¹² the same

number attended only in the second half of July 2019. It is thanks to these actors that the projects culminated in the staging of both plays. With the smaller groups, there was thus more of an opportunity for a certain type of successful collective action:

There is a probability of collective action occurring where the number of individuals forming the latent group is very limited. In this first case, the marginal contribution of each individual is significant. The effectiveness of collective action and in consequence the benefits that it can produce are dependent upon the participation of every individual. (Boudon and Bourricaud 1989, 20)¹³

The promoters of cultural centres generously provided space for the development and performance of the two shows. Equally, FLLAC's dean allowed *LCM* to be performed during the faculty's cultural days in July 2019 to members of the dean's office, teaching and admin staff, and students.

Throughout the entire creative process, there was opposition from almost every category of contributor. The former head of department was still against developing *RLI* due to the uncontrollable behaviour of a fair few students. There was conflict among learners when it came to choosing the subject matter for each play. Furthermore, students did not always agree with the lecturer-coordinator. In *RLI* for example, the lecturer wanted a reconciliatory conclusion where all actors would kneel down and say sorry. But this idea was rejected by the actors for ethical reasons. They had ideological ambitions founded in student activism and argued that it was not their responsibility to say sorry as "victims" of the invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year. The lecturer also had to provide a counter-argument to popular opinion when the students, who were strongly invested in opposition politics, wanted to keep the initial title of the second CC play, *Les Talons de Maman* (Mum's Heels), alluding to the surname of Benin's current president, Patrice Talon. According to the students, "this title was not at all insulting to whoever it may be because all men have heels". However, the coordinator believed that the title in question was a confrontational, risky, critical statement, especially considering the challenging political context underscored by the imprisonment of political opponents of the current government and the suspension of independent media. However, the coordinator could be accused of self-censorship and conformism when theatre in itself should be a subversive artistic practice.

Therefore, some students chose to adopt a strategy of avoidance or deception rather than disagree with the coordinator. They pretended to cooperate but did the exact opposite once they were on stage. This was the case with Student 1, the leading actor in *RLI* who acted contrary to stage directions during a performance of the play at the Benin French Institute in Cotonou on 29 September 2018; in the final scene, he knelt down with the other actors when he should have remained standing and acting alone as the rebel of the group. Questioned after the show, he said: “I’m not sure why I knelt down. I’m certain though, it wasn’t that I forgot. I just felt myself drop to my knees. It just came naturally.”¹⁴ An even more subtle strategy was that of hijacking, which involved redirecting the creative process to control it better.

This happened during the development stage of *LCM*. Three students stood out for the relative ease with which they worked, with really good ideas, when it came to acting technique (genuflexion, outstretched arms, working in pairs, etc.). As the story was being constructed, they skilfully established a clear plan and composed some good-quality lines for the play’s dialogue. In no time at all, the play was pretty much complete and took the form of a traditional dramatised story. However, the creative freedom of other participants was subdued and they pulled back. The coordinator was unaware of this. Luckily, he did realise that, while the aforementioned three students were on the UAC campus, they were using stereotypical frameworks and performative clichés employed by actors in the Ensemble Artistique et Culturel des Étudiants (Student Artistic and Cultural Assembly). Let’s take a look at the pros and cons of these strategies as part of the CC.

Aesthetic Challenges

First, we will define the challenges and then we shall look at how they were handled.

Stereotypes, Didacticism and Politicisation

The challenges of CC in the lecture hall included an outpouring of stereotypes, a lack of originality and excessive politicisation. *LCM* was reduced to a bunch of clichéd images, having been hijacked by the aforementioned trio of students. The pedagogical objectives were also not attained.

With regard to *RLI*, the aesthetics of the play and its significance were liable to suffer if Student 1 was left to act as he wished in the final scene. By kneeling down with the three other actors, he erased any meaning that could be derived from the contrasting

“kneeling/standing” postures. Regarding the need to apologise, Student 1 also created a false consensus, meaning that the play could be seen as dreadfully moralistic, something that had already been criticised during rehearsals.

The highly political tone of the initial title *Les Talons de Maman* (Mum’s Heels) added to the students’ impulsive militancy and could have transformed the creative process into a platform for the opposition party. Aside from the aforementioned safety risks, the play was drifting into what could be described as activist theatre. The former departmental head’s opposition could also be seen as an obstacle to the creative workshops. However, very early on in the process, this was established as a challenge to overcome, the idea being to convince the head of the educational advantages of such an initiative. It should be noted that the head constantly offered advice to the lecturer-coordinator and asked him to be cautious. Finally, the students’ inexperience in itself brought about aesthetic challenges. How were the different categories of people involved in CC able to overcome them, if only in part, when dealing with the actors as genuine strategic participants? The answer to this question lies in the staging and the direction of those actors.

Staging and Direction of Actors

In terms of staging, the coordinator’s work focused on several theatrical considerations analysed by Patrice Pavis: the actor; the alliance of voice, music and rhythm; and that of spatio-temporal factors, dramatic action and “other physical components of performance” (2001, 158). These three elements can be broadly regrouped into three categories: work on the actors; work on voice and costumes; and work on scenography, sound and lighting.

Work on the Actors: Seeking Stage Presence

According to Michel Pruner, after voice “the body is the second most important instrument in an actor’s expressive work” (2000, 165). This may well be true, but to overcome the aforementioned challenges, we first had to deal with the amateur actors’ corporeality. Early on in the process, working on the student actor’s body became a real necessity. The young artists were not able to imagine themselves in the skin of the theatrical character, so they did not produce the corresponding movements. In short, they had no stage presence, so they were unable to “situate themselves in the here and now for the public, acting as human beings that are ‘live’ without any intermediary” (Pavis 2004, 56). How could that be achieved when, considering the improvised nature of CC, the storyline and characters themselves were still

being developed? The coordinator had to take gradual steps, using trial and error, depending on the ideas that emerged from each and every contributor. For example, during the “warm-up”, which involved a mix of song, dance and poetry, he encouraged students to open up their emotions more and lose their inhibitions by repeating phrases such as: “I’m performing, so I’m working,” “I’m acting, so I see,” etc. He then urged them to just take to the stage and act because, he said, the “constitution recognises their right to make mistakes”. So, after the first *RLI* warm-up, four actors were asked to move around on stage following a simple instruction: “Imagine you’re students.¹⁵ You enter the lecture theatre, you’re waiting for the lecturer ...” After a few attempts, it became clear that the characters required more clarification; they needed distinct names and personalities. As a result, Student 1 became the group leader and main spy, Student 2 was the late arrival and seductress, Student 3 the coward, and Student 4 the chaotic one.

These definitions provided some initial direction on stage, helping the young artists to understand better what was expected of them. The characters inspired different words and dialogues, as can be seen below in *LCM*’s opening extract, when the children are proud to see their mother parading around in high heels:

Child 1: Mum has bought a new pair of shoes.

Child 2: Oh, what beautiful shoes!

Child 3: They are shoes Made in China!

Child 4: Shoes Made in Japan!

Child 5: Shoes Made in Europe!

Child 6: No, no, no! These are shoes Made in Benin!

[*Song in the Fon language*]

The repetition, which serves to emphasise the lexeme “shoes”, focused the audience’s attention on the pair of stilettos, symbolising the mother’s artificial rise to a position of power. This theatrical dialogue peppered with interventions in Fon, the national language (interjections, proverbs and incantations), was accompanied by mimesis and related movement.

During rehearsals, run-throughs, full dress rehearsals and then performances, the actors started to show stage presence and develop “the sympathy factor that brings about corporeality” (Pavis 2004, 167). Evidence of this could be seen in the use of space on stage (the Mother-President proudly walking around in her stilettos), mimesis and related movement (Student 1 mimicking his peers), the importance of dance sequences (the songs in *Fon*, the warlike choreography of students when faced with the police in *RLI*), etc. As Rose Acakpo writes:

Roi LMD International is conceived as a complete performance, integrating all artistic languages: songs in “Fon”, the national language, dances, eulogies, poetry, which allow the play to be anchored in its cultural context and confer upon it a theatrical identity, with an Italian-style staging and an aesthetic that sits between identification and detachment. (Acakpo 2018, 2)

Work on Voice and Costumes

The work on voice came next, though it was no less important. First, we focused on the most obvious component: intensity. The coordinator explained to actors in both *RLI* and *LCM* that the ability to be heard – to raise the voice without shouting – is the most important quality for any orator. This prerequisite was soon followed by other vocal requirements such as control of delivery, diction and intonation. For example, Student 1 took great pains to slow his diction down in certain scenes where that was required; he only started to roll his “r” in “*retardataire*” (latecomer) after several weeks of rehearsals. Errors of syntax, grammar and vocabulary also needed to be noted and corrected. This was a clear requirement for the oral performance; however, it was even more important when it came to writing the text. Members of the “transcribers/writers” group took notes throughout the development of *RLI* and these were collated and refined. This led to a text that was put forward to be revised collectively during a writing workshop held at the start of November 2017. The structure of the text remained faithful to the original plan, but that did not happen with the dialogue. Speeches were rewritten and great care was taken to achieve the correct style of writing.

Finally, the majority of actors in both *RLI* and *LCM* dressed in their ordinary student clothes so they would conform with the characters’ profiles. In *Roi LMD International*, the realism of the king’s costume (traditional shoes, cloth around the neck like the kings of Abomey) did not detract from his colourful and madcap personality (paper crown, badly knotted necktie,

patchy beaded necklace, sunglasses with just one lens ...). His costume performed two main functions: it was funny as it was amusing to the audience, and it was illustrative as it identified the actor as the “king” and supported “different interpretants of the dramatic text”. The audience could “see in him a manifestation of ideas, values, points of view and expressed feelings” (Vigeant 1989, 103). His heart attack is then symptomatic of the difficulties encountered in staging *RLI*, a difficult system to treat based on the prescription given by Student 4, performing the role of a doctor: “boxes of amphitheatraline”, “professoramine” tablets and a “pack of libraridone”. These neologisms – which were said in an ironic tone – represented different types of medicine and thus the ways to escape the crisis – i.e. by developing an adequate learning infrastructure and recruiting more teaching staff. During each performance of the play, it was no surprise that audience members (the majority of whom were students, but there were also youngsters who had left school early and some who were illiterate) showed their interest and understanding of the messages conveyed through laughter, applause and sometimes increased engagement, especially during the scene where there is a clash with the police. The scenography contributed in the same satirical manner as the dialogue and costumes.

Work on Scenography, Sound and Lighting

Defining the precise work involved in the practice of scenography, Marie-Noëlle Semet-Haviaras writes that:

Claiming to be a scenographer rather than a set designer is highlighting a mode of involvement that goes beyond designing and guiding the original work and calls for innovative effort, that of the creative artist. (Semet-Haviaras 2017, 21).

This “innovative effort” led to the creation of a simplified form of scenography that sat somewhere between realism and symbolism. Scenography in *LCM* was reduced to a chair, coins and banknotes on stage; in *RLI*, lumps of brick were used for the students’ seats and there was also a stand for the teacher and an oblong box containing a single book. When the coins and banknotes unexpectedly fell from the Mother-President’s clothing – tied, until that point, into a section of her *pagne* – this triggered a dramatic turn of events that darkened the previously glowing image of the head of state. It is no surprise then that at this precise moment in the show, the audience (made up of individuals from the dean’s office, teaching and admin staff, and students) applauded more than ever. The message was clear and the

socio-political context of the play was unmistakable. Both actors and audience realised the demagoguery of the Mother-President at the same time. The money served to change her status:

Functionally, this object becomes a *signifier*; it's a type of symbolic object conveying connotations that fall within the category of meaning and do not depend on its actual usage. (Vigeant 1989, 78)

The same can be said for lighting and sound, especially in *RLL*. Yellow spotlights could be seen in the lesson in the lecture theatre and also during Student 1's coronation, thereby suggesting the light of day and providing a temporal sign. The light switched to sustained darkness during the scatological mime, which served to indicate both the time of this nocturnal act as well as the students' secret and conspiratorial nature. The deep red light projected during the night-time rebellion against the police left the audience with the feeling of a bloody battle, further reinforced by sound (shots fired from a Kalashnikov, the noise of things breaking, etc.). Thus, the audience watched the image of an excessive conflict unfold, pitting the armed police against vulnerable students:

Student 3: Our stones are ready

David versus Goliath

The earthen pot and the iron pot

We will be victorious!

The students displayed their bravado through discursive intertextuality by referring both to the Bible ("David and Goliath" in 1 Samuel 17: 1–51) and to the Fables of Jean de La Fontaine ("The Earthen Pot and the Iron Pot" in Fable 2 of Book V). They soon scurried off, much to the amusement of the audience. However, the audience's reactions were not always enthusiastic. Individuals were also quick to express their disappointment, meaning that not all aesthetic challenges were overcome.

Challenges Not Entirely Resolved

Problems persisted with each one of the plays: command of the text, memory lapses, lack of knowledge regarding tricks to disguise those lapses from the audience, the recitative and

theatrical tone of some of the children's lines in *LCM*, movement that was too stiff and detached. There was also perceptible disharmony when it came to onstage group acting, which was particularly noticeable in the dancing and tone of voice in the militant songs of *RLL*.

However, it was in *LCM* that aesthetic issues continued to be a real challenge. Not only were there problems in terms of voice, but also with regard to acting and scenography (limited ability to use objects on stage and to give them new meaning), among other things. This could be explained by the lack of rehearsals and an urgency to perform the play during the FLLAC cultural programme of July 2019. Work with the actors really needed to continue over the holidays, but this proved very difficult as some individuals were unavailable. For the same reason – made worse by the social disruptions caused by the pandemic – the plays in the following two academic years did not reach completion. In 2019–20, there was *Chômage degré zéro* (Zero Degrees Unemployment) and in 2020–21, *30 heures pour vivre* (30 Hours to Live).

We decided it was impossible to complete this type of creative process in the lecture hall. The solution found comprised a redesign of the play's format; it was reduced in length, which inevitably had a significant impact on the storyline, the plot and the number of people involved. For example, instead of creating a one-hour play, they had to consider producing sketches of five to eight minutes, where everything was developed and staged in the lecture hall so that pedagogical objectives could hopefully still be attained.

Conclusion

Having carried out this study, it appears that training in theatre at the university is practical and *a fortiori* takes the form of CC, but it is far from being an epiphenomenon when it comes to the university's teaching provision. The process brought different categories of participant together and, because of this, CC became a dynamic social space where individuals from a range of habitus came together. Analysing issues arising from interactions during the process of creating *RLL* and *LCM* has highlighted the types of strategy used by participants in the theatre project as well as aesthetic challenges. The latter were picked up, in part, thanks to the methodology employed throughout the creative process. Interactions were sometimes a source of conflict, but as such were driving forces for CC if participants knew how to transform that conflict into a strength that could help bring the theatre project to a successful

conclusion. However, for a positive outcome in the lecture hall, there had to be a redesign of the format previously adopted for the plays. This is what it took for the students to be able to follow the creative process from start to finish before the end of the academic year.

The fact remains that, for now, we can be proud of the enthusiastic reception given by audiences attending performances of *RLI* and *LCM*. Indeed, the processes undertaken in creating these two plays evoke Augusto Boal's "Theatre of the Oppressed" in Latin America thanks to their innovative and participatory nature. But they do not follow the same principles as Boal's revolutionary art aesthetic, whereby the audience is made a participant in the play itself, shifting in status from "spectator" to "spect-actor".

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¹ An earlier version of this article was published in *Rilales: Revue Internationale de Linguistique Appliquée, de Littérature et d'Éducation* (Nouwligbèto 2021). It has been expanded and translated into English following double blind peer review for the *Journal of African Cultural Studies*.

² In this article, I, the author, refer to myself as the "lecturer-coordinator" or "coordinator" rather than "director". This title seems more accurate as it best reflects the spirit and philosophy of "collective creativity". My work consists of coordinating individual and combined efforts in the creative process.

³ INMAAC continues to suffer terribly from a lack of teaching personnel and suitable facilities. The majority of staff are temporary lecturers, permanent staff having been significantly reduced in number.

⁴ Quotations are translated by Georgina Collins, unless otherwise listed in the bibliography. Of course, collective creativity in Benin did not begin with this academic experiment. It is consubstantial with the artistic and cultural practices of traditional societies in Dahomey (now the Republic of Benin), where, for example, ceremonial dancing during healing rituals and sacred mask performances (Egungun, Zangbéto, Guèlèdè, etc.) were never the initiative of one individual, but very much involved the whole the community. This cultural collectivity served as the foundation for French-language sketches in the 1930s by Dahomean attendees of the William-Ponty Teacher's College in Senegal, both during the academic year and in the holidays spent in the colony of Dahomey. Since the 1960s, in a context characterised by a lack of theatre texts and their incompatibility with local socio-cultural realities, this method of theatrical creativity has been recaptured and expanded by groups such as the Ensemble national folklorique (National Folklore Ensemble), Les Cerveaux noirs (The Black Brains), Les Muses du Bénin (The Muses of Benin), Le Théâtre de l'IRAD (Theatre of the Dahomey Institute of Applied Research), Zama Hara, and the Ensemble Artistique et Culturel des Étudiants (Students' Artistic and Cultural Ensemble). For further details, see Bienvenu Koudjo (1976) and Fernand Nouwligbèto (2015, 2018, 2019, 2020).

⁵ The new definition of CC proposed here helps to underline the difference between CC and Total Theatre, defined as a “production that endeavours to use all available artistic resources to come up with a spectacle that appeals to all the senses, thereby creating the impression of totality and a wealth of meaning that overwhelms the audience” (Pavis 1998, 405). The CC stands out through its inclusive and participatory production process and not through its content. It may or may not lead to Total Theatre, which, in addition, can be achieved through the staging of a pre-existing text by an author or by a director or group of actors developing a theme. The CC is first a social process before it is an aesthetic practice: Total Theatre, on the other hand, is an “aesthetic ideal” (ibid., 405).

⁶ Students belonging to the Fédération Nationale des Étudiants du Bénin (FNEB; Benin's National Federation of Students) and the clandestine Communist Party of Benin were at the forefront of anti-establishment movements in the 1980s. And in the second half of that decade, amplified by the disastrous economic situation in Benin and trade union

demonstrations, they triggered the end of the Military Marxist regime (1972–89). For more on this subject, see Aimé Frédéric Hounzandji (2017, 310–357).

⁷ In the 1990s, the student trade unionisation crisis led to the birth of other rival federations in addition to the one already in existence, namely FNEB. They included the Union Nationale des Étudiants du Bénin (UNEB; Benin’s National Union of Students) and the Union Nationale des Scolaires, Élèves et Étudiants du Bénin (UNSEEB; National Union of Schoolchildren, Pupils and Students). UNEB had a reputation for being a pro-governmental student association close to President Nicéphore Soglo’s regime (1991–96), and that reputation remains to this day. However, UNSEEB is the student branch of the Communist Party of Benin and seen as very radical.

⁸ The root of these negative perceptions can partly be found in the extremely difficult studying conditions at UAC. The blatant lack of teaching staff and infrastructure as well as excessive student numbers explain the very high failure rates each academic year, especially in the *facultés classiques* (offering the more traditional subjects). Added to that are the ideological and political divisions that exist between teaching unions, in particular the Syndicat National de l’Enseignement Supérieur (National Union for Higher Education) and the Syndicat Autonome de la Recherche et de l’Enseignement Supérieur (SYNARES; Independent Union for Research and Higher Education). During the management of the 2015–16 crisis, SYNARES, which has communist convictions, was seen as an organisation that was very close to the students and therefore to the “people”. This is where the simplistic bipolarisation of the image of the teacher originates, the prevailing one being that of the “persecutor” who “downgrades” the students.

⁹ Interview with the author Tony Yambodé on the possibilities of a partnership between the DLM and the Espace Mayton Promo, Abomey-Calavi, 2018. Yambodé is director of the Espace Mayton Promo cultural centre, located close to UAC’s Abomey-Calavi campus.

¹⁰ The word “star” was regularly used by the former DLM head to mock a tendency among students (especially those responsible for the lecture hall) to show off in front of their peers.

¹¹ Rose Acakpo is a graduate teaching assistant on the “Theatre Studies” option. She teaches at the INMAAC/UAC and sometimes fills in at the DLM.

¹² Creating *RLI* was a very long process; it stretched out over more than six months. After the performance, there was the editing process and then the publication of the text. Students primarily worked over the holidays. In contrast, *LCM* was conceived and created in barely

three months, the majority of work being carried out in the second half of July 2019, right before the holidays.

¹³ Of course, the collective action being discussed here is collective creativity.

¹⁴ Interview with the actor Patrice Ogou (Student 1), Cotonou, 2018. We believe that the actor knelt down so he wouldn't be seen taking a rebellious stance in front of lecturers in the audience from the DLM.

¹⁵ Of course, they were all students! But, there is a huge difference between a student who just peacefully follows his studies and one who plays the character of a student on stage. In the latter, it's all about acting awareness.